

Topic:***The Impact of Psycho-Yogic Intervention on Altering Eating Attitudes in Young Adults Prone to Eating Disorders*****Dr.Kirti, Dr. Santosh Vishvakarma*****Dept. Of Psychology, Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya, Shantikunj, Haridwar*****Abstract**

The prevalence of eating disorders among young adults poses significant health risks and challenges. This study investigates the effects of psycho-yogic practices—integrating yoga, mindfulness, and psychological counseling—on modifying eating attitudes in young adults at risk for eating disorders. A sample of 60 participants, aged 18-25, underwent a 12-week psycho-yogic intervention. The Eating Attitudes Test (EAT-26) was administered before and after the intervention to assess changes in eating behaviors and attitudes. Results indicated a significant reduction in dysfunctional eating attitudes in the intervention group compared to the control group. These findings suggest that psycho-yogic practices may serve as an effective intervention for preventing eating disorders among vulnerable populations.

Keywords: Psycho-yogic practices, eating attitudes, young adults, eating disorders, mindfulness

1. Introduction

Eating disorders, including anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, and binge eating disorder, are complex mental health conditions that often emerge during adolescence and young adulthood. The National Eating Disorders Association (2022) reports that approximately 30 million people in the United States will struggle with an eating disorder at some point in their lives. These disorders are characterized by severe disturbances in eating behaviors, distorted body image, and significant emotional distress, leading to serious physical health consequences (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

Young adults are particularly vulnerable to developing disordered eating patterns due to societal pressures, peer influences, and the pursuit of an ideal body image (Levine & Murnen, 2009). Traditional treatment approaches often include psychotherapy and nutritional counseling; however, these methods may not adequately address the psychological and emotional factors that contribute to eating disorders.

Psycho-yogic practices, which integrate yoga and mindfulness techniques with psychological counseling, have emerged as a promising alternative. Yoga promotes physical well-being and mindfulness, fostering a more positive relationship with one's body and self (Kabat-Zinn, 2003). This study aims to explore the effectiveness of psycho-yogic practices in altering eating attitudes among young adults prone to eating disorders.

1.1 Historical Background: Sir William Gull originally diagnosed anorexia nervosa in the late 19th century, attributing it to moral weakness. Since then, eating disorders have been better understood. Research revealed the intricate interaction of psychological, cultural, and biological elements that cause disordered eating, moving attention from morality to medicine and psychology. CBT, which targets maladaptive ideas connected to disordered eating, became a dominant treatment in the late 20th century (Fairburn et al., 2003). Jon Kabat-Zinn's Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) promoted present-moment awareness in mental health therapy in the 1970s (Keng et al., 2011). Psycho-yogic practices emerged from the popularity of

mindfulness and yoga as complementary treatments for body image and self-acceptance issues. This integration addresses the emotional issues behind eating disorders by including body awareness, anxiety reduction, and emotional control, giving potential prevention and treatment options for vulnerable groups.

1.2 Research Significance:

This research fills a vacuum in the existing body of literature about integrated psycho-yogic interventions. These interventions aim to improve dysfunctional eating attitudes by including mindfulness, yoga, and psychological counselling. Psycho-yogic techniques offer a comprehensive approach by boosting bodily awareness and emotional regulation, both of which are useful for persons who are at risk for developing eating disorders. This research is to examine the efficacy of a structured psycho-yogic intervention for young adults who are at risk. The research will draw from core ideas in mindfulness (Kabat-Zinn, 2003) as well as current studies on yoga for body image (Culbert et al., 2015).

2. Literature Review:

The prevalence of eating disorders in India is increasing, especially among young adults and adolescents, influenced by Western ideals of beauty and thinness. Research indicates that the swift sociocultural transformation, propelled by globalization and media, has led to a rise in body dissatisfaction and disordered eating behaviours among urban Indian populations (Nayak & Raju, 2018). Indian society has traditionally linked health to well-rounded body types; however, this view is gradually shifting towards a preference for slimmer body ideals, especially among youth influenced by global media standards (Sharma & Coutinho, 2016). As a result, the prevalence of eating disorders, including anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, and binge eating disorder, is increasing, presenting new challenges for mental health professionals in the country.

Conventional treatment approaches in India have primarily utilised cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) and nutritional counselling; however, researchers emphasise the necessity for culturally sensitive and holistic interventions. Psycho-yogic practices that combine yoga and mindfulness with psychological counselling present a viable alternative. Yoga, an established practice in Indian culture, is acknowledged for its physical benefits as well as its role in improving emotional balance, body awareness, and self-acceptance (Khalsa et al., 2015). The integration of yoga into therapeutic practices is regarded as a culturally appropriate method that enhances the acceptability and accessibility of treatment for Indian patients. Additionally, mindfulness-based practices resonate with traditional Indian philosophies that prioritise mental clarity and the regulation of desires (Sahni et al., 2015).

Studies indicate that mindfulness and yoga each play a significant role in enhancing body image and alleviating anxiety in individuals exhibiting disordered eating behaviours (Singh & Goyal, 2020). Nevertheless, research focussing on the synergistic effects of psycho-yogic interventions in India is scarce. Psycho-yogic interventions adopt a holistic approach aimed at addressing the physical, emotional, and cognitive aspects of eating disorders. This methodology may improve treatment outcomes by alleviating stress, enhancing body image, and promoting a positive

relationship with food. Cultural factors significantly influence attitudes towards body image and health; thus, a psycho-yogic intervention may provide a culturally appropriate solution for India's increasing issues with eating disorders. This study aims to examine the effects of psycho-yogic practices on eating attitudes in young adults in India, thereby enhancing the existing, albeit limited, literature on culturally specific interventions for eating disorders.

Mindfulness and yoga are linked to beneficial effects on emotional control, self-acceptance, and body image (Culbert et al., 2015). Mindfulness meditation specifically promotes present-moment awareness, demonstrating potential in mitigating binge-eating behaviours (Brown & Ryan, 2003). Although mindfulness and yoga have been examined separately, there is a paucity of research investigating their synergistic benefits in psycho-yogic therapies designed to modify disordered eating behaviours.

This study seeks to fill this gap, examining the outcomes of a psycho-yogic intervention on eating attitudes among young adults.

3. Methodology

3.1 Participants

A mixed-methods strategy was employed, consisting of a survey and a quasi-experimental investigation. The study utilised purposive sample to enlist 300 young individuals (150 male, 150 female) for the evaluation of eating attitudes. From this pool, quota sampling identified 100 individuals (50 experimental and 50 control) for an 8-week psycho-yogic intervention. The intervention comprised yoga practices and psychoeducational sessions. Pre- and post-assessments were administered with the EAT-26 and psychological well-being measures. Quantitative data were examined using statistical tests, whilst qualitative insights were obtained through theme analysis. Ethical guidelines were adhered to, encompassing informed consent and data confidentiality.

3.2 Intervention

The psycho-yogic intervention lasted 12 weeks and consisted of weekly 60-minute sessions. Each session included the following components:

Yoga Practice (Surya-Namaskar): Each session begins with a brief check-in period (5 minutes) to set intentions and reflect on the past week's progress or challenges. The primary practices include Surya Namaskar (15 minutes), which consists of a dynamic sequence of 12 yoga postures to enhance body awareness, promote physical strength, and induce mental relaxation. The focus is on connecting breath with movement, cultivating mindfulness, and fostering a positive relationship with the body.

Pranakarshan Pranayama: Breath control methods were instructed to enhance relaxation and mindfulness, aiding participants in cultivating heightened awareness of their physiological sensations and emotional states. a systematic breathing technique designed to regulate prana (vital
Mindfulness Meditation: Mindfulness Meditation is a cognitive training technique that instructs individuals to decelerate rapid thoughts, relinquish negativity, and soothe both the mind and body. It integrates meditation with mindfulness, described as a mental state of complete concentration on the present moment, allowing for the acknowledgement and acceptance of thoughts, feelings, and sensations without energy),

alleviate anxiety, and foster inner tranquilly. Participants practise conscious inhaling and regulated exhalation cycles to equilibrate energy flow and improve concentration. Five cycles in fifteen minutes daily.

Psychological Counseling based on CBT: This study employed cognitive-behavioral strategies to confront and modify negative thinking patterns around food and body image, aiming to cultivate healthier attitudes and behaviours in participants. Daily group counselling sessions were held with groups of 10 participants, fostering a friendly atmosphere for individuals to share experiences, learn together, and enhance collective resilience. During these sessions, individuals were instructed to recognise and reframe erroneous beliefs, formulate positive affirmations, and employ coping techniques to address disordered eating thoughts. Alongside group sessions, participants had individualised assistance through 10-15 minute sessions conducted biweekly, allowing focused interventions customised to their distinct needs and concerns. This integrated group and individual methodology provided a thorough, supportive framework to bolster the transformational cognitive changes essential for enduring transformation.

3.3 Measures

The primary outcome measure was the Eating Attitudes Test (EAT-26), a widely used screening tool for disordered eating attitudes and behaviors. The EAT-26 consists of 26 items rated on a 6-point Likert scale, with higher scores indicating more maladaptive eating attitudes. Secondary measures included:

Body Image Scale (BIS): Assessed participants' perceptions of their body image.

State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI): Evaluated participants' levels of anxiety.

3.4 Procedure

Participants took the EAT-26 and secondary assessments before and after the 12-week intervention. Data analysis includes paired and independent t-tests to compare pre- and post-intervention changes within and across groups. The psycho-yogic intervention began with written agreement from participants and ran in stages. Participants received a one-week introduction to yoga and a brief explanation of eating disorders (EDs) including symptoms, significance, and intervention needs.

The primary intervention period included daily 10-person group counselling and individual counselling for twice a week. Yoga featured Surya Namaskar, performed in groups often for 15 minutes and 12 rounds. Ten-person Pranakarshan Pranayama had five cycles every session. Consciousness and emotional control were promoted during 15-minute mindfulness meditations with precise instructions. Participants were interviewed after the 12-week psycho-yogic intervention to evaluate its efficacy.

Graph: 1

4. Results

4.1 Participant Characteristics

Descriptive statistics for the pre-test revealed that the intervention group had a mean EAT-26 score of 21.72 (SD = 2.654), while the control group had a mean score of 21.52 (SD = 2.104). An independent samples t-test confirmed no significant difference between the groups at baseline, with a mean difference of 0.20 ($t = 0.295$, $df = 48$, $p = 0.769$). The 95% confidence interval for the mean difference was between -1.162 and 1.562, indicating that both groups had comparable eating attitudes before the intervention.

4.2 Primary Outcomes

In the post-test, the intervention group showed a significant reduction in EAT-26 scores, with a mean of 15.36 (SD = 3.147), compared to the control group's mean of 21.24 (SD = 2.006). The Levene's test for equality of variances was significant ($F = 5.157$, $p = 0.028$), indicating unequal variances between groups. Thus, the independent samples t-test was interpreted under the assumption of unequal variances. The post-test t-test yielded a significant result ($t = -7.877$, $df = 40.734$, $p < .001$), with a mean difference of -5.88. The 95% confidence interval ranged from -7.388 to -4.372, suggesting that the psycho-yogic intervention led to a statistically significant reduction in disordered eating symptoms in the intervention group compared to the control group.

Graph: 2

4.3 Secondary Outcomes

The change in mean scores from pre-test to post-test showed a notable reduction in maladaptive eating behaviors in the intervention group, with a mean reduction of 6.36 points (from 21.72 to 15.36). In contrast, the control group exhibited a minimal change, with a mean reduction of only 0.28 points (from 21.52 to 21.24), further supporting the effectiveness of the intervention.

Change in Mean Scores of Maladaptive Eating Behaviors (Pre-test to Post-test)

Graph: 3

4.4 Result Analysis

The findings indicate a clear and significant effect of the psycho-yogic intervention on improving eating attitudes among young adults at risk for eating disorders. At baseline, both the intervention and control groups displayed comparable EAT-26 scores (mean difference = 0.20, $p = 0.769$), confirming that there were no significant differences in eating attitudes prior to the intervention.

However, post-intervention results reveal a substantial decrease in EAT-26 scores for the intervention group, with a mean score of 15.36, compared to the control group's mean of 21.24. The t-test analysis confirmed this reduction was statistically significant ($t = -7.877$, $p < .001$), with a mean difference of -5.88 and a 95% confidence interval between -7.388 and -4.372, underscoring the intervention's efficacy.

Additionally, the intervention group showed a marked decrease in maladaptive eating behaviors, with a mean reduction of 6.36 points compared to just 0.28 points in the control group, highlighting the intervention's strong impact. These results suggest that psycho-yogic practices effectively improve eating attitudes by fostering greater body awareness, reducing anxiety, and enhancing emotional regulation. This aligns with existing research, supporting the therapeutic value of mindfulness and yoga in reducing disordered eating behaviors and promoting self-acceptance.

5. Discussion and Interpretation

The results substantiate the hypothesis that psycho-yogic interventions positively impact eating attitudes among young adults at risk of eating disorders. The significant reduction in EAT-26 post-test scores for the intervention group, as evidenced by the t-test analysis, highlights the intervention's success in fostering healthier eating behaviors and body image perceptions. These findings align with previous research, which shows that mindfulness and yoga practices improve self-acceptance and reduce disordered eating behaviors (Sahni et al., 2015; Culbert et al., 2015). The mechanisms behind these effects likely involve enhanced body awareness, anxiety reduction, and improved emotional regulation, facilitated through mindfulness practices (Kabat-Zinn, 2003).

This study examined the impact of a psycho-yogic intervention on eating attitudes among young adults at risk for eating disorders. The findings support the hypothesis that psycho-yogic practices, which combine mindfulness, yoga, and psychological counseling, can significantly improve eating attitudes and reduce maladaptive eating behaviors. Prior to the intervention, no significant differences were observed between the intervention and control groups, indicating a comparable baseline in eating attitudes (mean difference = 0.20, $p = 0.769$). However, post-intervention results showed a substantial reduction in EAT-26 scores for the intervention group, suggesting that participants benefitted meaningfully from the psycho-yogic program.

The statistical analysis revealed a significant difference in post-test scores between groups ($t = -7.877$, $p < .001$), with a mean reduction of 5.88 points in the intervention group. Additionally, the intervention group demonstrated a notable decrease in maladaptive eating behaviors, reducing by an average of 6.36 points on the EAT-26, compared to just a 0.28-point reduction in the control group. These results align with previous studies indicating that mindfulness and yoga practices positively impact eating attitudes by fostering self-acceptance, reducing anxiety, and enhancing emotional regulation (Sahni et al., 2015; Culbert et al., 2015).

The significant post-intervention reduction in EAT-26 scores aligns with theoretical frameworks suggesting that mindfulness and body awareness can mediate positive changes in eating behaviors. Mindfulness techniques, which were integral to the psycho-yogic intervention, may have contributed to increased awareness and regulation of emotional triggers associated with disordered eating (Kabat-Zinn, 2003). Through enhanced emotional regulation, participants could develop healthier attitudes

towards food and body image, reducing the likelihood of engaging in maladaptive eating patterns.

These findings have practical implications for mental health professionals and educators working with young adults at risk for eating disorders. Integrating psycho-yogic interventions in clinical or educational settings could provide a complementary approach to traditional therapies, potentially improving treatment outcomes by addressing both physiological and psychological aspects of disordered eating. However, further research with a larger sample size and long-term follow-up is recommended to confirm the sustainability of these effects and explore potential applications across diverse populations.

In summary, this study reinforces the therapeutic value of psycho-yogic practices in promoting healthier eating attitudes and suggests that mindfulness-based approaches may offer substantial benefits for young adults with disordered eating tendencies. These findings provide a foundation for future research into holistic approaches to eating disorder prevention and treatment.

5.1 Limitations

While the findings are promising, the study is not without limitations. The relatively small sample size and short duration of the intervention may affect the generalizability and sustainability of the results. Additionally, the lack of a long-term follow-up limits the ability to assess the lasting impacts of the psycho-yogic practices.

5.2 Future Directions

Future studies should include long-term follow-up assessments to evaluate the sustainability of the observed effects, expanding to larger and more diverse samples for broader generalizability. Comparative studies with traditional therapies can highlight the unique benefits of the psycho-yogic approach, while exploring underlying mechanisms of change could deepen our understanding of its impact. Individualized interventions, gender-specific analysis, and integration of additional practices like guided imagery and advanced meditation techniques may enhance effectiveness. Incorporating objective measures, assessing integration into clinical settings, and evaluating cost-effectiveness will ensure practical applicability and accessibility, maximizing the potential of psycho-yogic practices as preventive and therapeutic tools for disordered eating.

6. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that psycho-yogic practices can be an effective intervention for altering eating attitudes in young adults prone to eating disorders. By integrating mindfulness and psychological support, these practices may foster a more positive relationship with food and body image, contributing to the prevention of eating disorders among vulnerable populations.

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